

Research Data Management Lifecycle Checklist

Project Title: _____

Planning: Plan ahead

Plan & Design

- Capture Key Project Information
- Review Relevant Policies for Data Management
- Write or Review a DMSP
- Budget for Data Management and Sharing
- Define Roles and Responsibilities
- Establish Data Organization
- Keep Up to Date with Data Management Resources and Policies

Active Research: Document

Collect & Create

- List Data Types, Formats, and Size
- Outline Data Collection Methods
- Utilize Metadata Standards
- Create Data Documentation

Analyze & Collaborate

- Facilitate Data Analysis
- Maintain Code Documentation
- Document Data Analysis Protocols
- Document Image Management and Processing

Checklist Completed by:

Name: [First-Last]

Date: [YYYY-MM-DD]

Operational Storage: Think short and long term

Store & Manage

- Secure Active Data
- Determine Appropriate Data Storage Locations
- Create a Data Backup Plan
- Resolve Access Permissions

Evaluate & Archive

- Assess Data Retention
- Appraise Data for Archiving
- Appropriately Dispose Data

Dissemination: Share confidently

Share & Disseminate

- Determine Data Ownership and IP
- Review or Create Data Use Agreement(s)
- Fulfill Data Sharing Requirement(s)
- Apply Open Science Practices

Publish & Reuse

- Connect Scholarly Products
- Select Appropriate Data Repository(ies)
- Confirm FAIR Data Principles

Checklist Reviewed by:

Name: [First-Last]

Date: [YYYY-MM-DD]